

Researches in the Thiazole Series. Part I. Action of Hydrochloric Acid on Allylthiosemicarbazide.

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By the action of bromoalkylamines on potassium thiocyanate Gabriel (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1189, 2280, 2984) obtained substances which he called derivatives of ψ -propylene thiocarbamide and which are now known to be derivatives of thiazole. Also Prager (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 2991), on condensing allylamine with mustard oils, obtained products, which, on treatment with hydrochloric acid, were transformed into thiazole derivatives.

The above results led me to try the action of hydrochloric acid on various 4-allylthiosemicarbazides. It should be mentioned that Busch and Lotz (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1914, 90, 270) tried the action of boiling hydrochloric acid on 4-allylthiosemicarbazide; they found that the semicarbazide either remained unchanged or decomposed into its components on prolonged boiling.

The author has obtained from 4-allylthiosemicarbazide a hydroxylmethylthiazole (II) which appears to be formed by the decomposition of the hydrazine derivative (I) first formed.

It was then thought that by substituting acetyl, benzoyl, or phenyl in the hydrazine residue of allylthiosemicarbazide, a thiazole derivative might be obtained that on hydrolysis would give a thiazole hydrazine. But during acetylation of allylthiosemicarbazide an acetyl derivative of allylimino-*C*-methylthiobiazole was formed (Pulvermacher, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 626). The benzoyl derivative could be prepared and when treated with hydrochloric acid it was transformed not into a thiazole but into a thiobiazole derivative, the reaction proceeding according to the scheme—

Substitution by phenyl group, as in 1-phenyl-4-allylthiosemicarbazide, led to the formation of a thiazole derivative.

A further attempt was made to prepare a thiazole hydrazone by means of benzylideneallylthiosemicarbazide; this led to hydroxymethylthiazole. When the hydrazone residue in allylthiosemicarbazide was substituted by the phenyl thiocarbimide group the resulting allylanilidothiosemicarbazide yielded a thiobiazole derivative. The process possibly took place according to the scheme—

From these experimental facts it appears that if the 1-position in allylthiosemicarbazide is unsubstituted the thiazole hydrazone probably first formed readily parts with the hydrazone residue and hydroxymethylthiazole results; but if this position is occupied by certain groups or radicals then either a thiazole or a thiobiazole ring is formed. The question which groups or radicals favour the formation of one ring or the other is now under investigation and will form the subject of a subsequent communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Hydroxymethylthiazole.—4-Allylthiosemicarbazide (10 g.) was heated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (20—25 c.c.) in a sealed tube at 100° for 2—3 hours. After cooling the tube contained a small quantity of crystals of hydrazone hydrochloride which were separated; when the filtrate was diluted with water and then saturated with ammonia, the free base separated in needles or rectangles having a faint reddish tinge. Crystallised from boiling benzene it formed white needles, m.p. 200°. The yield was very poor. The substance is easily soluble in alcohol and benzene but insoluble in water. (Found: S, 27.12. C₃H₇ONS requires S, 27.35 per cent.)

Acetylmethylthiazole.—The monoacetyl derivative was prepared in the usual way by heating for 10—15 minutes. On cooling crystals separated which were collected and crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 242°. (Found: S, 20.28. C₆H₈O₂NS requires S, 20.13 per cent.)

Benzoylmethylthiazole.—The hydroxymethylthiazolone was warmed with benzoyl chloride for a few minutes and the excess of benzoyl chloride was destroyed by means of alkali. The benzoyl

derivative so obtained formed a semi-solid mass which was allowed to remain in the alkaline solution for about two days when it gradually solidified. The solid mass was collected, finely powdered and triturated with an alkaline solution and filtered. The residue was washed with water and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 243°. (Found: S, 14.66. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2NS$ requires S, 14.48 per cent.)

Nitrosomethylthiazole.—An aqueous solution of sodium nitrite was added to the hydrochloric acid solution of hydroxymethylthiazole cooled in ice. The nitroso-derivative separated at once in the form of a yellow precipitate which was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from acetic acid: light yellow needles, m.p. 188°. (Found: S, 21.67. $C_4H_6O_2N_2S$ requires S, 21.92 per cent.)

Phenylhydrazidomethylthiazole.—Molecular quantities of allyl mustard oil and phenylhydrazine were mixed together in a flask. The reaction began with evolution of heat and after a few minutes the whole mass assumed a jelly-like appearance. The reaction was brought to completion by heating on a water-bath for half an hour. The product was dissolved in boiling alcohol and from this solution 4-allyl-1-phenylthiosemicarbazide separated in long white needles, m.p. 119°. This semicarbazide (10 g.) was heated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) in a sealed tube at 100° for 2 hours. After cooling, the tube contained crystals having a light tinge and the acid solution had a pink colour. These crystals were collected and dissolved in water, boiled with animal charcoal, and the filtrate concentrated when the hydrochloride of phenylhydrazidomethylthiazole separated in colourless needles, m.p. 203°. To obtain the free base the following method was found best: the aqueous solution of the hydrochloride was warmed on a water-bath and to the hot solution ammonia was slowly added until neutral, when the base separated in almost white plates. These were collected, washed and dried. So obtained the substance melted at 92° and was used for the preparation of its derivatives. For analysis a portion was dissolved in alcohol, the solution boiled with animal charcoal and from the filtrate it was precipitated by water in white plates, m.p. 94°. (Found: S, 15.68. $C_{10}H_{11}N_2S$ requires S, 15.46 per cent.)

The *acetyl derivative* was prepared in the usual way. It was purified from alcohol when it was obtained as white needles, m.p. 190°. (Found: S, 18.16. $C_{11}H_{12}ON_2S$ requires S, 12.85 per cent.)

The *benzoyl derivative* prepared in the ordinary way, solidified on long standing. The solid was collected and crystallised from boiling benzene. It is insoluble in alcohol, ether, chloroform and cold benzene and moderately soluble in hot benzene. (Found: S, 10·88. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_2S$ requires S, 10·29 per cent.)

The *benzylideneallylthiosemicarbazide* was obtained by adding the equivalent quantity of benzaldehyde to a hot alcoholic solution of 4-allylthiosemicarbazide. After a few minutes white needles of the benzylidene compound separated which was crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 125°. (Found: S, 14·49. $C_{11}H_{13}N_3S$ requires S, 14·38 per cent.)

Benzylidenehydrazidomethylthiazole.—The benzylidene compound (15 g.) was heated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (80 c.c.) in a sealed tube at 100° for two hours. The contents of the tube were diluted with water and saturated with ammonia when the free base separated in white rectangular crystals. It was purified from alcohol from which it crystallised in shining rectangles, m. p. 141°. (Found: S, 14·69. $C_{11}H_{13}N_3S$ requires S, 14·38 per cent.). On hydrolysis it gave the hydroxymethylthiazole previously described.

The *acetyl derivative* was prepared and crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 119°. (Found: S, 12·42. $C_{13}H_{15}ON_2S$ requires S, 12·26 per cent.)

The *benzoyl derivative* separated from alcohol in white rectangles, m. p. 150°. (Found: S, 10·22. $C_{13}H_{17}ON_2S$ requires S, 9·91 per cent.).

The *nitroso derivative* was obtained by adding an aqueous solution of sodium nitrite to the cold hydrochloric acid solution of the thiazole. The yellow precipitate was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 120° with decomposition. (Found: S, 12·68. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_2S$ requires S, 12·90 per cent.)

Acetylallylimino-C-methylthiobiazole.—Allylthiosemicarbazide was boiled with acetic anhydride. The acetyl derivative separated on cooling and crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 79°. When the acetyl compound was deacetylated with hydrochloric acid it gave the hydrochloride of allylimino-C-methylthiobiazole (m.p. 173°) which on neutralisation with ammonia yielded the base as a crystalline mass. It crystallised from alcohol in white plates and melted at 126° and was identical with Pulvermacher's compound obtained from allylthiosemicarbazide, and acetyl chloride.

Allylimino-C-phenylthiobiazole.—4-Allyl-1-benzoylthiosemicarbazide was prepared from allylthiosemicarbazide and benzoyl chloride in chloroform solution; the product crystallised from boiling water in needles, m. p. 172°. On heating this benzoyl compound with hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube at 100° it was converted into the hydrochloride of the above thiazole (m.p. 112°). The free base was obtained by saturating the dilute acid solution with ammonia. Crystallised from dilute alcohol it melted at 118°. It was identical with the compound obtained from 4-allyl-1-benzoylthiosemicarbazide and acetyl chloride (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 628).

Allyliminothiobiazolethiol.—Allylthiosemicarbazide was converted into allylthiocarbanilidothiosemicarbazide by boiling with phenyl mustard oil in alcoholic solution for two minutes. The solid product was filtered and washed with alcohol. It was thus obtained in plates, m.p. 188°. This thiosemicarbazide was then heated in a sealed tube at 100° with concentrated hydrochloric acid for two hours. On cooling a white precipitate separated. The mother-liquor, on dilution with water, became turbid and after some time deposited a further quantity of the white substance. For purification it was dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide solution and precipitated by dilute acid. Crystallised from boiling water in plates it melted at 136°. (Found: N, 24·87. C₈H₇N₃S₂ requires N, 24·28 per cent.). From the dilute acid solution on neutralisation with alkali a small quantity of another substance was obtained which could not be purified and studied.

Oxidation of Benzylidenemethyl-thiazole hydrazine and Hydroxymethylthiazole.—The hydrochloride of each (8 g.) was shaken up with excess of bromine water and the mixture was first warmed on a water-bath and finally heated to boiling over a free flame. The mixture was then evaporated to dryness when a brown syrup was left behind. This was extracted with alcohol and the alcoholic solution allowed to stand for a long time in a desiccator. The crystals that separated were collected and crystallised from water. It was found to be identical with the ψ -methyltaurin of Gabriel and Prager (*loc. cit.*).

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